

**LINEAR SYSTEM WITH TIME-DEPENDENT SQUARE $(n \times n)$ -MATRIX:
A BRIEF REMARK
ON
SPECTRAL THEORY OF ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS**

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ABSTRACT. Brief remark—as the subtitle suggests—whose subject, neither more nor less, is expressly indicated in the title.

KEYWORDS: linear system, time-dependent, square $(n \times n)$ -matrix.

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1. Linear System with Time-Dependent Square ($n \times n$)-Matrix

This is not an article, but a *petite remarque* with the aim of provoking *very general suggestions*. It is the sequel to a query that arose in an email coming from T. Lehner, regarding the manuscript [8, sec. 3].

Query 1.1 (*Subject of discussion*). Take a linear system of the kind

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = M(t)y(t), \quad y \in \mathbb{F}^n,^{\mathbf{a}} \quad t \in I_t, \quad (1)$$

with time-dependent $n \times n$ square matrix $M = m_{ij}(t)$, $ij = 1 \dots n$, on the interval $I_t \subset \mathbb{R}$. Of course, t (time) is the independent variable, and it is pretended to be real (that is, belonging to the continuous 1-dimensional and Dedekind-complete ordered \mathbb{R} -field), whilst the functions can be real- or complex-valued. What is the best solution (it is just a manner of speaking, really), *c'est-à-dire* the (most) advantageous solution, of Eq. (1)?

1.1. Some Techniques

Some techniques for solving the linear system Eq. (1) are mentioned by T. Lehner and C. Cambon [8]:

(1) Wentzel–Kramers–Brillouin–Jeffreys approximation [16] [7] [1] [5], which has its roots in the Liouville–Green method [9] [10] [11] [12] [2],

(2) involvement & ad hoc modifications of Levinson’s theorem [15], for long-time and asymptotic behaviors.

2. Resolution Tips

Omne tulit punctum qui miscuit utile dulci.^b
— Q. HORATIUS FLACCUS [4, v. 343, p. 421]

A perfect way (Horacian rule) to answer the Query 1.1 is to mix usefulness with pleasure, transfusing the latter into the beautiful and elegant.

Interlude: Useful, Pleasant, and Beautiful

A spirit like that of H. Weyl would have gone even further; he would not have delayed to embrace Keats’s adage [6, p. 297]: «[...] “Beauty is truth, truth beauty” — that is all Ye know on earth, and all ye need to know». G.H. Hardy [3, p. 85] is enthroned on this side, caught in ecstasy of aesthetics: «The mathematician’s patterns, like the painter’s or the poet’s, must be *beautiful*; the ideas, like the colours or the words, must fit together in a harmonious way. Beauty is the first test: there is no permanent place in the world for ugly mathematics».

2.1. Homogeneous System of Linear Ordinary Differential Equations

An equality like Eq. (1) is of a homogeneous type. Its solution is obtainable from the fundamental matrix of solutions. To understand this, it may be enough to write an equation linear with a first derivative of a function, see Eq. (4).

2.1.1. Simple Form

But let us start from a simple form, such as

$$\frac{dy_i}{dt} = \varphi_i(t)y_n, \quad (2)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Its solution comes from the derivatives of

$$y_i = y_i(t), \quad (3)$$

which is an unknown function, according to these two procedures:

(1) reduction of the equation in question into a differential equation of order n , or into a fistful of differential equations whose order must be less than n ,

^a The \mathbb{F} -field is for \mathbb{R} -field or \mathbb{C} -field, as usual.

^b «Whoever mixed the useful with the pleasant obtained all the votes», namely «won everything».

(2) the integrable combinations procedure.

2.1.2. Passing thru the Wrońskian, I

We now analyze the case of an equation thus specified,

$$\dot{y} = M(t)y \quad (4)$$

which replicates, in the resolution methodology, the equation under query.

Theorem 2.1. *Eq. (4) respect a fundamental system of solutions.*

Proof. Let us impose

$$y(t_0)_{t_0 \in [\alpha, \beta]} = (y_0^1, \dots, y_0^n) \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} y_0^i, \quad i, \dots, n. \quad (5)$$

The fundamental system of equations w.r.t. $y^i(t)$ is dependent on a scalar-valued determinant, called *Wrońskian* [13, § 194, p. 224],^a which I here symbolize with W_s .^b If it is different from zero, the theorem is consequently proved, ou seja $W_s(t_0) \neq 0$, and

$$W_s(t) = \begin{vmatrix} y_1^1 & y_1^2 & \cdots & y_1^n \\ y_2^1 & y_2^2 & \cdots & y_2^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ y_n^1 & y_n^2 & \cdots & y_n^n \end{vmatrix} \neq 0, \quad (6)$$

for $t_0 \in [\alpha, \beta]$, $\alpha \leq t_0 \leq \beta$. □

Marginalia 2.1 (Variable coefficients). Let us take the example of an equation

$$y^n + m_{n-1}(t)y^{n-1} + \cdots + m_1(t)\dot{y} + m_0(t)y = \varphi(t). \quad (7)$$

Under the Cauchy problem, the initial values of y and y -derivatives are

$$\begin{cases} y(t_0) = y_0^0, & (8a) \\ \dot{y}(t_0) = y_1^0, & (8b) \\ \cdots & \\ y^{n-1}(t_0) = y_{n-1}^0, & (8c) \end{cases}$$

Eq. (7) is easily transformed into

$$\dot{y}_0 = y_1, \quad (9a)$$

$$\dot{y}_1 = y_2, \quad (9b)$$

$$\cdots$$

$$\dot{y}_{n-2} = y_{n-1}, \quad (9c)$$

$$\dot{y}_{n-1} = -m_{n-1}(t)y_{n-1} - \cdots - m_0(t)y_0 + \varphi(t), \quad (9d)$$

going to change each variable. If Eq. (7) is equal to zero, then it is, again, transformable into

$$\dot{y} = My_{(\varphi)}, \quad (10)$$

fixing

$$y_{(\varphi)} = \begin{cases} y, & (11a) \\ \dot{y}, & (11b) \\ \cdots & \\ y^{n-1}, & (11c) \end{cases}$$

^a This determinant was named by T. Muir in honour of J. Hoene-Wroński.

^b The subscript letter \mathbf{s} will be for *scalar* function.

and an identification of the matrix

$$M \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} [M]^{n \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdot & 1 \\ -m_0 & -m_1 & -m_2 & \cdots & -m_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

2.1.3. Passing thru the Wrońskian, II

The solution of Eq. (1) lies in the same vein as the proof of Theorem 2.1.

Let $f(t) = f_1(t), \dots, f_n(t)$ be a vector function, i.e. a vector-valued function, for $n \in \mathbb{F}$ (real- or complex-valued) functions f_1, \dots, f_n . The Wrońskian determinant is

$$W_s(f_1, \dots, f_n)(t) = \begin{vmatrix} f_{11}(t) & \cdots & f_{n1}(t) \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ f_{1n}(t) & \cdots & f_{nn}(t) \end{vmatrix}, \quad t \in I_t. \quad (13)$$

The basis will be defined by

$$f_k(t) = f_1 u_1 + \cdots + f_n u_n, \quad (14)$$

where $v_i = v_1, \dots, v_n$ is the unit vector.

If $W_s(t) \neq 0$, one has the aforementioned fundamental system of solutions $f_1(t), \dots, f_n(t)$.

If $W_s(t) = 0$, the result is zero for all $t \in I_t$.

It should be noted that, for $i = j$, one gets

$$\dot{W}_s(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n m_{ij}(t) \begin{vmatrix} y_1^1 & y_1^2 & \cdots & y_1^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ y_j^1 & y_j^2 & \cdots & y_j^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ y_n^1 & y_n^2 & \cdots & y_n^n \end{vmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

Eq. (15) is equal to $\sum_{k=1}^n m_{k(k)}(t)W_s(t)$, so

$$\sum_{k=1}^n m_{k(k)}(t) = \frac{\dot{W}_s(t)}{W_s(t)}. \quad (16)$$

Put

$$\text{tr}(M) = \sum_{k=1}^n m_{k(k)}(t). \quad (17)$$

By integrating, Eq. (16) gives

$$W_s(t) = \left\{ W_s(t_0) \exp \left(\int_{t_0}^t \text{tr}(M(s)) ds \right) \stackrel{\text{eqv}}{=} W_s(t_0) \exp \left(\int_{t_0}^t \sum_{i=1}^n m_{i(i)}(s) ds \right) \right\}. \quad (18)$$

2.2. Non-homogeneous System of Linear Ordinary Differential Equations

A non-homogeneous system have these appearance:

$$\dot{y} = M(t)y + \varphi(t), \quad (19)$$

the initial condition of which can be

$$y(t_0) = y_0. \quad (20)$$

Here too $y(t)$ and $\varphi(t)$ are vector-valued functions in n -dimension whose continuity holds in $\alpha \leq t \leq \beta$. The 1st-order form, for a linear differential equation, derived from (19), will be

$$\frac{dy_i}{dt} = m_1^i(t)y_1 + \cdots + m_n^i(t)y_n + \varphi_n^i(t), \quad (21)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n$. The following two methods are usually used to solve equation à la (21):

- (1) the integrable combinations procedure,
- (2) the Euler–Lagrange variation of arbitrary constants procedure.

CODA: THE FLYING PIGS OF MATHEMATICS

H. Poincaré [14, p. 157] writes, with not too subtle sarcasm:

[P]our démontrer un théorème, il n'est pas nécessaire ni même utile de savoir ce qu'il veut dire. On pourrait remplacer le géomètre par le *piano à raisonner* imaginé par Stanley Jevons; ou, si l'on aime mieux, on pourrait imaginer une machine où l'on introduirait les axiomes par un bout pendant qu'on recueillerait les théorèmes à l'autre bout, comme cette machine légendaire de Chicago où les porcs entrent vivants et d'où ils sortent transformés en jambons et en saucisses. Pas plus que ces machines, le mathématicien n'a besoin de comprendre ce qu'il fait.

We often have the idea that mathematics is a logical box from which to automatically extract information, as with the legendary machine in Chicago mocked by Poincaré, where «pigs go in alive and come out transformed into hams and sausages». It is not so. Mathematics, in addition to a rigid logical rib, is mostly a discipline endowed with an extensible structure, the extensibility of which is made possible by the faculty of the imagination. And the only pigs it knows are the flying ones of its own creation.

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